

ANALYSIS OF REDUCED DECODING COMPLEXITY OF LOW DENSITY PARITY CHECK DECODER

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ABSTRACT

The approach of this paper to reduce decoding complexity of Low density parity check decoder(LDPC). For that technique uses high precision soft messages at the variable node and put down the message length, due to this number of interconnection between check node and variable node will reduce. For the designing and simulation purposes LDPC uses min-sum algorithm. In min-sum algorithm quite increment in complexity so modified min-sum algorithm is use to reduce decoding complexity. A design model of this decoder uses for long distance communication application such as WiMax, WLAN, DVB-S2 and optical communication. The results achieve significant reduction hardware of LDPC decoder

KEY WORDS

Digital communication; error correction coding; iterative coding; min-sum algorithm.

1. Introduction

In recent years Low density parity check codes [1] have become one of the most attractive error correction code because of its marvelous performance [7] . The LDPC gain high degree of parallelism architecture [2] for the sake of high data rate application such as WiMax, DVB-S2, WLAN and optical communication [5]. Performance of LDPC Decoder is depends upon the complexity of

the underlying algorithm. Sum product algorithm can achieve high bit error rate (BER) performance but there is requirement of hardware resources for the implementation [11]. Various algorithm have been approaches to maintain balance trade-off between decoding complexity and its performance. Min-sum algorithm (MSA) is simplified version of sum product algorithm to reduce hardware complexity and without performance degradation of LDPC decoder [10].

LDPC code is currently considered as a next generation coding scheme for the communication system .Because of flexibility of LDPC code it is possible to achieve balance trade-off between decoding performance and decoding complexity. All the decoding nodes and their interconnection to be realized in hardware with the help of fully parallel architecture of LDPC decoder to achieve throughput in several Giga bits per second (Gbps) [4]. Therefore LDPC code is approaches by several protocols such as Digital Video Broadcasting via satellite (DVB-S2), Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN) , World interoperability for Microwave Access (WiMax). Due to high speed performance of LDPC decoder many researcher are attracted towards to implement high speed LDPC decoder [8]. For getting such performance is possible to LDPC

decoder by ASIC implementation of fully parallel architecture. The sum product algorithm [9], a soft-decision based message passing algorithm can achieve good decoding performance but slight increment of hardware complexity. Bit flipping is hard decision algorithm getting least complexity but suffers from poor performance [9]. Min-Sum algorithm is simplified version of sum product algorithm which uses simple arithmetic and logical operation required for that. The min-sum algorithm performs suboptimal iterative decoding which is less complex than sum-product algorithm. The performance of this algorithm is impacted by quantization of soft input messages. As requirement of higher level of quantization, the hardware complexity is also increases and for reducing the quantization level, hardware complexity is less but degradation of performance is occur.

This paper design an algorithm which reduced interconnect complexity and check node operation. By taking min-sum algorithm [12] as a reference, the algorithm, namely modified min-sum algorithm (MMS) is used for designing of a LDPC decoder. These algorithms are independent of the hardware architecture [15][16]. So, in this paper, fully parallel architecture has been designed for analysis and verification. Result of Modified Min-Sum algorithm reduce the decoding complexity.

2. Low Density Parity Check Code

The representation of LDPC code by means of parity check matrix. There are two types of LDPC code, the first is LDPC block code [1] and another LDPC convolutional code [13]. Among both LDPC block code mostly used for its practically hardware implementation. LDPC convolutional codes are presented in terms of matrix or graphically. In graphical representation LDPC code is characterized by bipartite graph. The representation of LDPC code by means of parity check matrix. There are two types of LDPC code, the first is LDPC block code [1] and another LDPC convolutional code [13]. Among both LDPC block code mostly used for its practically hardware implementation. LDPC convolutional codes are presented in terms of matrix or graphically. In graphical representation LDPC code is characterized by bipartite graph which is also known as Tanner graph. Tanner graph consist of two types of nodes namely variable node and check node. Variable node deals with codeword bits and check nodes associated with parity check constraints. The generalized operation of LDPC is that variable node provide the input bits to check node unit whereas it performs parity check operations and gives updated output bit again to the variable node unit. The 1-component of parity check matrix which, it may be comes from rows or columns are associated with Tanner graph through edges and these edges are connected to nodes called as degree of node. If the degree of check nodes and variable nodes are constant then that code called as regular LDPC code otherwise it said irregular LDPC code. Irregular LDPC code slightly violates its performance [14][3], therefore regular LDPC

code is mostly prefer to get desired performance for VLSI implementation.

$$H = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

A. LDPC matrix

B. Tanner Graph representing LDPC

3. Decoding Algorithms for LDPC

The min-sum algorithm is a modified version of sum-product algorithm [6], due to min-sum algorithm the non-linear operation of sum-product algorithm is reduce. The quantization length of soft input messages also known as Log-likelihood ratio (LLR)..

A. MIN-SUM ALGORITHM

The operation of variable node (V) and check node (C) in min-sum algorithm are as shown below [15].

Variable node: $V_i = LLR_n + \sum_{j \neq i} C_j$ (1)

Where, $n=1,2,\dots,N$ (variable node)

$i, j=1,2,\dots,dv$ (degree of variable node 'n')

Check node: $C_k = \prod_{l \neq k} \text{sign}(V_l) \times \min_{l \neq k} |V_l|$ (2)

Where $l, k= 1,2,\dots,dv$ (degree of check node)

B. Modified Min-Sum Algorithm

This algorithm passes 2-bit extrinsic message between variable node and check node which require 4-bit intrinsic message for variable node operation [15][16],by using above techniques reduce the interconnect complexity. Hence variable node require to map 2-bit message to 4-bit message and vice versa. The variable node and check node operation of modified min-sum algorithm (MMS) is given as.

a) Variable node operation

The operation of variable node operation of MMS is same as standard min-sum algorithm except that in MMS variable node uses precision quantized [16] LLR operation as given in equation (3) . The above operation getting 2-bit message which consist of sign bit and magnitude bit . The threshold T_m considered as reference for mapping 4-bit message to 2-bit message. Equation (4) shows the function for mapping 4-bit to 2-bit message.

$V_i = g\{ LLR_n + \sum_{j \neq i} C_j \}$ (3)

where, $n= 1,2,\dots,N$ (variable nodes)
 $i, j=1,2,\dots,dv$ (degree of variable node 'n')

$$g(y) = \begin{cases} 01 & \text{if, } y > T_m \\ 00 & \text{if, } 0 \leq y \leq T_m \\ 10 & \text{if, } 0 > x \geq -T_m \\ 11 & \text{if, } x < -T_m \end{cases} \dots\dots(4)$$

b) Check node operation

In check node operation product of sign bit of incoming message and minimum magnitude bit of incoming message is determined . The XOR operation is use to compute sign bits of check node and minimum magnitude bits are determined using AND operation. By cascading sign bit and magnitude bit the output of check node message (Ck) is obtained. This message is continuously passing through node so that maximum iterations are obtained.

$$S_k = V_1^{(s)} \oplus V_2^{(s)} \oplus \dots \oplus V_l^{(s)} \quad \forall l \neq k \quad \dots(6)$$

$$M_k = V_1^{(m)} \& V_2^{(m)} \& \dots \& V_l^{(m)} \quad \forall l \neq k \quad \dots(7)$$

$$C_k = \{S_k M_k\} \quad \dots(8)$$

Where $l, k = 1, 2, \dots, dc$ (degree of check node)

S= Sign bit of check node messages

M= Magnitude bit of check node messages

$V_l^{(s)}$ = Sign bit of message 'l' from variable node

$V_l^{(m)}$ = Magnitude bit of message 'l' from variable node

4. Architecture of LDPC Decoder

Modified min-sum algorithm updated the variable node structure whereas it requires LUTs for mapping 4-bit to 2-bit and vice versa. In variable node architecture 2-bit input is received from check node and 4-bit quantized LLR input and produce updated 2-bit output to check node. Here addition and subtraction block is taken to for mapping operation otherwise design is to be design level [16].

Fig. a. Block diagram of LDPC decoder

Fig b. Generalized operation of LDPC decoder

a) Optimization of LDPC Decoder :-

Fig c. Block Diagram of Variable Node Structure

Fig d. Block Diagram of Designed Variable Node Structure of un-optimized Architecture

Fig e. Block Diagram of Designed Variable Node Structure of optimized Architecture
----- 2- bit message ——— 4- bit message

5. Simulation and Result

a. Check Node

The variable node architecture of Un-optimized and Optimized architecture is analyzed with the help of device XQ5VLX30T, VIRTEX-5Q family. The analysis result of both architecture are given as

Parameters	Un-optimized Architecture	Optimized Architecture
Registers	11	11
LUT's	50	22
f/f's	8	7
No. of IOB	21	21
Defense grade Virtex-5Q family XQ5VLX30T Device		

Table 1. Comparative analysis of optimized and un-optimized architecture

6. Conclusion

In this paper apply the desire decoding algorithm , decoding techniques and others parameters for getting desired response to reduce the decoding complexity. capacity. By analyzing the un-optimized and optimized

architecture of variable node operation to reduce the decoding complexity. With the help of modified min-sum algorithm compute the variable node unit and check node unit in order to save the hardware overhead in LDPC decoder.

7. References

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